

HOMOEOPATHIC PREPARATION OF LYCOPODIUM CLAVATUM EMPHASIZING THE IMPORTANCE OF MENTAL SYMPTOMS ON DIFFERENT DISEASES - A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Background: The mental state reflects the essence of an individual and holds utmost importance in understanding the patient. It is believed that illnesses initially manifest on the mental plane before any physical changes occur. According to the principles of Hahnemann and Kent, mental and emotional symptoms take precedence over physical symptoms. Lycopodium being one of deep acting Homoeopathic medicine, it has great efficacy in various diseases. **Aim and objective:** This review aims to explore the significance of mental symptoms and evaluate the effectiveness of Lycopodium in treating various disease. The objective is to know how mental symptoms are important and its effectiveness of drug lycopodium in different diseases. **Methods:** Literature search was conducted among different electronic databases and various homoeopathic books. 24 articles were finally included in this study. The results of the literature search presented in a flow chart. The data of the articles was tabulated. **Results:** This review consists of 24 articles that mentioned mental generals in their study and the intervention is lycopodium. This review consists of 1 double blind randomised placebo-controlled trail, 1 observational study, 22 case report/series/study. This review explores about efficacy of lycopodium in many diseases. **Conclusion:** In conclusion, this review highlights the significance of mental symptoms in the prescription and emphasizes their role in achieving holistic treatment outcomes in homeopathy. Lycopodium found successful in treating various diseases. Many more studies are necessary to establish an evidence-based results.

KEYWORDS- Chronic diseases, Homoeopathy, Lycopodium clavatum, Mental generals, Personality, Temperaments.

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INTRODUCTION

Homeopathy is a medical system that follows the principle of "Similia Similibus Curentur". It emphasizes holistic and individualized treatment for patients. The process of potentization enhances the latent medicinal properties of substances. ⁽¹⁾ Drug proving is done on healthy human beings. Individualization is the process of distinguishing and separating a person from other members of his group based on his peculiar and distinctive traits, both in health and disease. The patient is treated holistically and as an individual. Besides individualization, the patient's age, lifestyle, diet, occupation, domestic situation, mental state, and temperament should also be considered to determine how these factors might influence the disease and the potential for cure. Overall, a comprehensive understanding of the patient's individual circumstances and mental well-being is essential in guiding the treatment approach. ⁽¹⁾ Coming to the personality of Lycopodium Clavatum, its wide-ranging traits made it more prominent. The standard Lycopodium image depicts and that is "intellectually sharp but of weak muscular power." ⁽²⁾ The simplest method for recognizing it, particularly in illnesses involving bodily issues, is to grasp the individual's mental condition.

Understanding the mental state is the simplest approach to spot it (particularly in diseases with body pathology). Understanding the mental state is the most effective approach to identifying symptoms (particularly in diseases with body pathology). Start by prioritizing the symptoms that are most distinctive to the patient, followed by those that are progressively less distinctive, until you have addressed the common and non-distinctive symptoms, arranging them in a sequential order from the beginning to the end.

MATERIALS AND METHODS-

Eligibility criteria-This review encompassed studies that focused on the use of *Lycopodium clavatum* as an intervention for treating various diseases. The study included research that met the following criteria: 1) The intervention utilized the homeopathic remedy *Lycopodium clavatum*, 2) Only full-text articles were considered, 3) Articles published in the English language were included, 4) Studies mentioned mental symptoms/generals, and 5) Human trials were included. On the other hand, studies that did not have full-text available, involved in-vitro or in-vivo experiments, animal trials, or studies where mental symptoms were not addressed were excluded from the analysis.

Search methods- Literature search was conducted using terms *lycopodium clavatum*, mental generals, chronic diseases, temperaments, homoeopathy, personality using Boolean query. In addition, the process involved manually tracing back through a list of references to locate the desired information. A thorough search was conducted across a range of Homeopathic literature to gather relevant information presented in Prisma flowchart in (Fig. No.1).

Information sources- PubMed, google scholar, the Cochrane library, science direct, CORE-HOM, were among the electronic database were used to find the studies on homoeopathy intervention being *lycopodium clavatum*.

This review incorporated a total of 24 publications that specifically focused on *Lycopodium clavatum* in various diseases, and which mentioned mental generals. This study consists of 1 double-blinded randomized placebo-controlled trial, 1 observational study, and 22 evidence-based case reports, studies, or series. Details of the articles were organized in a tabular format in (Table.1).

Fig. 1. Prisma Flow Chart

Table. 1 Studies prescribed with Homoeopathic medicine Lycopodium clavatum

S.no	Article in brief	Study design	No. of cases prescribed Lycopodium	Assessment tool	Mental generals used in case for prescription	Results
1	Androgenic alopecia treated with individualised homoeopathic medicine. ⁽⁷⁾	Case study	1	Photographic evidence	Loss of self-confidence.	Improvement in the physical and psychological well-being.
2	Diabetic nephropathy in complete repertory. ⁽¹⁸⁾	Case study	1	Blood sugar levels were measured.	Ailments from Death of father, Helpful, Believes in own philosophy	Improvement in health with no new complaints.
3	Individualised treatment for Benign prostatic hyperplasia. ⁽⁹⁾	An evidence-based case series	1	Ultrasonography of whole abdomen before and after treatment, IPSS Score.	Obstinate, Irritable	The ultrasound report indicates a reduction in prostate size to 15 g
4	Celiac disease with single medicine. ⁽¹¹⁾	Case study	1	TTA IgA antibody Before and after treatment.	Desire to be alone, Violent Anger.	Improved
5	Generalised anxiety disorder. ⁽¹⁶⁾	Case report	1	HAM-A and Modified Naranjo Criteria, ORIDL	Aversion to quarrelling, anticipation-stage fright, fear of dark.	Improvement, measured by the Hamilton Anxiety Scale.
6	Alopecia areata with lycopodium. ⁽⁸⁾	Case report	1	Photographic evidence, before and after treatment.	Desire company, can't remain alone, Anger violent, Anger from contradiction	Regrowth of hair, as substantiated by photographic evidence
7	Diabetes mellitus with	Case study	1	HbA1C reports before 1 st prescription,	Irritability, desire for	Improvement

	lycopodium. (12)			and after 3,5,7,9 follow ups.	company, restless.	
8	Plaque psoriasis with individualised homoeopathic medicine (14)	Case report	1	Photographic evidence, Psoriasis Area and Severity Index score.	Aversion to work, Fear of people, Loss of self-confidence	Improvement in PASI Score-1
9	Lycopodium in Vitiligo. (17)	Case study	1	Photographic evidence for every follow up.	Irritability, Desire alone, Anxiety about her complaint, weeping without any cause, consolation aggravate, Anger due to contradiction	Improvement.
10	Ureteric calculi with constitutional medicine. (22)	Case report	1	USG reports before and after treatment, numerical rating scale for pain and photographic evidence of stone expelled after treatment.	Anxiety about health, Irritability, Ambitious, Want of self- confidence.	Improvement confirmed by ultrasound with no stones or cortical cysts.
11	A case study of benign prostatic hyperplasia. (10)	Case study	1	Ultrasonograp hy of Prostate, Uroflowmetry, Prostate Specific Antigen, digital rectal examination.	Desire for company, Anticipating anxiety, Dictatorial, domineering, dogmatic, and despotic, Cowardice, Sentimental, Fastidious, better by Consolation,	Improvement in IPSS score
12	Ovarian cyst with homoeopathy. (25)	Case report	1	USG	She loved company. She was an intellectual person, Calm and quiet disposition.	The post- treatment ultrasound revealed no abnormalities.

13	Urinary Stones with Constitutional medicine. ⁽²¹⁾	Case report	1	Ultrasonography.	Avaricious, Diligent, Introvert, Anxious about health, Intelligent.	No stone was found in the USG report.
14	Individualised approach of homoeopathy in tinea cruris. ⁽²⁶⁾	Case report	1	Photographic evidence	Lack of confidence, Reserved, Weeping alone, Stage fear	Improvement
15	Plaque psoriasis with constitutional medicine. ⁽¹⁵⁾	Case report	1	PASI score, photographic evidence, Modified Naranjo Criteria Score.	Anxiety, confusion of mind, depression (sad, melancholic), petulant, apprehensive, forgetful.	Improvement, reducing PASI score and Modified Naranjo Criteria
16	Recurrent urinary tract infection. ⁽²⁷⁾	Case report	1	Routine examination of urine before and after treatment.	Desire for company, Forgetful.	Improved
17	Schizophrenia. ⁽²⁴⁾	Case study	1	PANSS score, Modified Naranjo Criteria.	Ailments from fright, cowardice, Irresolution, reserved, delusions of persecution.	PANSS total score reduced
18	Schizophrenia with homoeopathy. ⁽²³⁾	A prospective, non-comparative, open-label observational study	36.	Intensity of symptoms-brief psychiatric rating scale score before and after treatment	Fear to be alone, Greedy, Irritable on contradiction, Complaints from fright, Fear when alone.	Improvements in the BPRS scale.
19	Management of urolithiasis. ⁽¹⁹⁾	Randomised double blind placebo controlled trial.	Verum(n=63), placebo(n=71)	Visual Analogue Scale	Irritability/getting anger easily, Contradiction intolerance, Want of self-confidence .	Lycopodium clavatum, did not demonstrate significant efficacy in expelling/dissolving kidney stones

						compared to placebo. However, there was a notable improvement in flank pain and a positive trend in dysuria, suggesting some potential benefits.
20	Venous ulcer and stasis dermatitis. ⁽²⁸⁾	Case series	1	CEAP, VCSS and photographic evidence, MONARCH.	Suicidal thoughts due to personal problems; Fearful dreams of dead people, snakes and animals.	Even after stopping the medication for three years, there were no instances of ulcer recurrence. The eczema also resolved; however, there were still lingering issues with skin discoloration and vein tortuosity.
21	Chronic Cholelithiasis with 50th millesimal potency. ⁽²⁹⁾	Case report	1	Ultrasonography, Modified Naranjo criteria.	Irritability, Fear of being alone, Tendency to weep easily.	Ultrasound evidence confirming the absence of stones.
22	Hyperuricaemia with nephrolithiasis. ⁽²⁰⁾	Case report	1	Ultrasound-kidneys, ureters and bladder, Modified Naranjo Criteria score, photographic evidence of expelled stone.	Want of self-confidence, desire for company, confusion.	Evidence indicating the expulsion of calculi from the body.
23	Alopecia areata. ⁽⁶⁾	case series	1	Photographic evidence.	Apprehensive nature, Great hurriedness in general, Anxious about his complaints.	Improved
24	Sweet Sugar Managed with Sweet Pills. ⁽¹³⁾	Case study	1	BSL-F and BSL-PP were mentioned in follow up chart.	Ailments, from anxiety, contradiction from anger, aversion to company,	BSL-F:98; BSL-PP:120, these results were observed in last follow up.

					weakness of memory.	
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DISCUSSION:

The patient's mental state and temperament play a vital role in the selection of a homeopathic remedy. These aspects are considered distinct and unique symptoms that should not be overlooked by the physician. Their accurate observation is crucial for identifying the most appropriate remedy for the individual. ⁽¹⁾ According to the principles of Hahnemann and Kent, mental and emotional symptoms take precedence over physical symptoms. The mental state reflects the essence of an individual and holds utmost importance in understanding the case. It is believed that illnesses initially manifest on the mental plane before any physical changes occur. A similar study was made on prescribing on mind symptoms and importance of mental generals. These studies explained that homeopathy is a holistic method of treatment, where they treat patient as a whole.

In this study, the significance of mental symptoms is highlighted. Mental symptoms are the first to emerge and persist throughout the testing process. They can be subjective or objective, and even observed in unresponsive individuals. Homeopaths emphasize the importance of mental symptoms for a comprehensive understanding of the patient, leading to improved treatment outcomes. ⁽⁴⁾

Mental/emotional symptoms take precedence over physical symptoms according to Hahnemann and Kent. The mental state reflects the core of an individual and is of utmost importance in understanding the case. Illness initially manifests on the mental plane before physical changes occur. This report describes a female patient who presented with white patches on the outer side of her right index finger and some spots on the back of her right hand. These skin manifestations appeared after experiencing a period of grief. Ignatia amara, prescribed based on mental symptoms, successfully resolved the patches, confirming homeopathy's efficacy for local conditions. ⁽⁵⁾

Conclusion

Homeopathic intervention Lycopodium showed a significant role in treating various diseases. A thorough case history must be taken because the mental symptoms are of significant and essential importance in establishing the pattern of totality. Through case-taking, it is necessary to form a proper totality. However, fewer RCTs had been conducted. For the scientific validation, additional research using an appropriate research design is therefore required in order to demonstrate the evidence-based efficacy of homeopathic treatment.

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